

MANAGEMENT PROBLEM BASED LEARNING MODEL IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF ECONOMIC LEARNING (CASE STUDY AT SMA NEGERI 2 AND SMA 5 CIMAHI)

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Abstract

A model is a three-dimensional representation of a real object. A learning model is a plan or pattern that is used as a guide in planning classroom learning or learning in tutorials. Problem based learning is a learning approach that gives students the freedom to plan learning activities, carry out projects collaboratively, and ultimately produce work products that are can be presented to others. "A learning model is basically a form of learning that is depicted from beginning to end, which is presented in a unique way by the teacher, including approaches, strategies, methods, techniques and even learning tactics that have been connected into a unified whole. Based on the opinions of these experts, researchers concluded that a learning model is a learning pattern that is depicted from beginning to end, a learning process that is presented specifically by the teacher to achieve learning goals. One learning model is a problem-based learning model. The problem-based learning model is innovative learning that is student-centered and determines the teacher as a motivator and facilitator, where students are given the opportunity to work autonomously to construct their learning. 5 The problem based learning (PBL) model is a learning model that involves a problem in the learning process. "The problem based learning model is a learning model that uses problems or activities as media." 6 The problem-based learning model is the assignment of tasks to all students to be done individually, students are required to observe, read and research. Based on several definitions, the researcher concludes that the problem-based learning model is learning which focuses on students' activities to be able to understand concepts and principles by conducting in-depth research on a problem and looking for relevant solutions and students learn independently and the results of this learning are products.

Keywords: Management Model Based Learning.

INTRODUCTION

The mandate of Law Number 12 of 2012 Article 35 paragraph 3 concerning curriculum states that the Higher Education Curriculum is developed by each Higher Education Institution with reference to Permenristekdikti No. 44 of 2015 concerning National Standards for Higher Education which must include Religion, Pancasila, Citizenship and Language Education courses. Indonesia is one inseparable unit. Director General of Higher Education Intan Ahmad in his speech in the 2016 PKN book mentioned the national character revolution agenda in Nawacita. That General Compulsory Courses (MKWU) in tertiary institutions are a source of values and guidelines in the development and implementation of study programs to deliver. Students strengthen their personalities so that they are consistently able to realize basic religious and cultural values, a sense of nationality and lifelong love of their country.

Increasing the ability to think, feel and behave in a more dignified manner as a basis for building the surrounding environment known as General Education so that graduates exist and are ready to face global challenges and behave more integratively with various scientific disciplines. Furthermore, the Directorate General of Learning in his speech emphasized more specific implementation of curriculum content. The implementation of the Higher Education Curriculum (KPT) in accordance with the National Higher Education Standards and referring to the Indonesian National Qualifications framework (KKNI), followed up by writing textbooks which can be used as a source of MKWU learning activities in order to educate graduates with Indonesian national character. The subject matter in this book is deliberately presented using a student-centred learning activity approach (Student Centered Learning/SCI). The learning carried out is an educational process through critical, analytical, inductive, deductive, reflective thinking processes and triggers "high order thinking": through participatory creative dialogue to achieve an understanding of the truth of the basic substance of the study, do real work and foster lifelong learning motivation in line with General Education concept. 3 In Indonesia SCL is known as active student learning (CBSA) and is implemented in the 2013 curriculum as a strategy in scientific learning. Student-based learning is believed to be very effective in improving the learning process in order to achieve optimal student learning outcomes. This is in accordance with the philosophy of learning, that learning is an activity of acquiring new knowledge where the more knowledge students gain, the greater their opportunity to continue to improve the quality of their attitudes and behavior. This view is in line with the learning approach developed by the cognitive psychology school which believes that students are rich in information. knowledge can explore new learning sources, either alone or together with a peer group. That way, they can obtain a lot of new knowledge and continue to add new conclusions (Dede Rosyada, 2015). As has been explained, the student-centered learning (SCL) model is the starting point for the mandate in implementing general compulsory subject learning. The learning model in question is the pattern of interaction between students and lecturers in the classroom which concerns strategies, approaches, methods and learning techniques applied in the implementation of teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Leadership style is a consistent pattern of behavior shown by a leader and known by other parties when the leader tries to influence the activities of other people. Leadership style is also a pattern of behavior of a leader in the process of mobilizing and influencing workers.

The outbreak of the Covid-19 virus or better known as corona in Indonesia has shaken all aspects of life. All areas of social life are affected, including education. This virus is global and currently the Covid-19 virus has infected 186 countries in the world and may now increase. Those who become victims of corona violence continue to increase. This virus does not respect age, rank, position. Whatever he is, whoever he is, everyone has the opportunity to be attacked.

This virus also forces social life to change, including adjustments to learning models and methods. So far, educators have focused more on conventional learning methods, namely face-to-face in class between teachers and students or lecturers and students. The learning process, discussions, questions and answers, and guidance all take place face to face. However, during the pandemic teachers had to adapt, adapting various types of learning models that can be implemented in online learning, one of which is the problem based learning model which aims

to improve the quality of learning. One innovation that can be carried out in learning is by implementing a learning model. Learning models play an important role in the learning process, as an effort to overcome boredom and increase students' active learning. One learning model that focuses on student centered learning and can be used in online learning is the problem based learning model. Problem Based Learning is a learning model that can train students to learn and collaborate in groups in an effort to find solutions to solve real problems. Based on interviews with several teachers, not all teachers are able to implement the learning model in the learning system. Therefore, problem based learning model training for economics teachers in Sukabumi City needs to be carried out in an effort to improve the quality of online learning in quality schools depending on the leadership's expertise in managing all existing resources to achieve the stated vision and mission. As stated, school progress is very dependent on the figure of the leader within the school. High school leaders are not only the principal but also include the Head of Skills Competencies, Deputy Principals, and all those involved. They are the ones at the forefront of driving activities and setting school targets.

One student-centered learning method is problem-based learning (PBL). According to Barrows (1992) problem-based learning (PBL) is a learning method that is based on the principle of using problems as a starting point for the process of gaining and integrating new knowledge. PBL is learning that is administered by presenting a problem, asking questions, facilitating investigations, and opening up space for dialogue. This paper tries to create a paper on the problem-based learning (PBL) model in carrying out sub-discussion assignments for the Citizenship Education course. Referring to the previous explanation, the author intends to conduct a literature study in order to understand the conceptual, procedural and assessment aspects for implementing PBL.

The standards that must be managed include the standards of educators and education personnel as the spearhead of educational success, namely teachers. Teachers must have abilities that enable them to carry out their duties and functions at school. A teacher's ability or competency is influenced by his or her leaders at school. The leadership style of school leaders can give special meaning to teachers' professional competence as educators. The leadership style of school leaders is expected to improve the performance of teachers, students and other educational components. An educational paradigm that gives broad authority to school leaders in developing their various potentials requires improving their abilities in various managerial aspects, in order to achieve goals in accordance with the vision and mission of their school.

Schools are complex and unique institutions. It is complex because the school as an organization contains various dimensions which are interconnected and determine each other. While the unique nature shows that the school as an organization has certain characteristics that other organizations do not have. The characteristics that make a school have its own character are the teaching and learning process and the place where human life is cultivated. Because of its complex and unique nature, schools as organizations require a high level of coordination and the success of the school is the success of the school leadership. Successful school leaders are those who understand the existence of schools as complex and unique organizations, and are able to carry out the role of school leader as someone who is given the

responsibility to lead the school. The problem based learning model can be used effectively to increase students' learning activity, so that the quality of online learning during the Covid-19 pandemic can be achieved well. The implementation of the problem based learning model for teachers needs to be supported through various forms of education and training. This statement is in line with the opinion of Fuadi and Muchson (2020: 25), the problem based learning model can be implemented by teachers through experience managing classes, participation in ongoing formal education and training. In general, learning begins with giving problems which aim to stimulate students' thinking patterns, in an effort to improve 4C abilities (communication skills, collaboration skills, critical thinking and problem solving skills, creativity and innovation skills). Educators' efforts to build 4C skills in the 21st century can be implemented through various forms of learning models that are more focused on solving authentic problems that can be solved cooperatively, so as to increase students' active learning (Arnyana, 2019: 5). Arends (2008:55) writes that there are 5 steps in implementing problem based learning, namely (1) orienting students to the problem; (2) organizing students to research; (3) assisting independent and group investigations; (4) develop and present work results; (5) analyze and evaluate the problem solving process.

The problems used in problem based learning are problems faced in the real world. Even though individual abilities are required for each student, in the learning process using the problem based learning model students learn in groups to understand the problems they face. Then students study individually to obtain additional information related to problem solving. The role of the teacher in problem based learning is as a facilitator in the learning process. Meanwhile, the stages in problem based learning model management according to Ibrahim & Nur (Juhari and Muthahharah, 2020: 213), are as follows. 1) Stage 1 (Orientation/Recognition of Problems for Students): At this stage, the teacher explains the learning objectives, proposes phenomena to raise problems, motivates students to get involved in problem solving, 2) Stage 2 (Organizing Students to Learn): At this stage, the teacher helps students to define and organize learning tasks related to problem solving, 3) Stage 3 (Guiding Individual/Group Investigation): At this stage, the teacher encourage students to collect appropriate information, carry out experiments to obtain explanations and solve problems, 4) Stage 4 (Developing and Presenting Work Results): At this stage, the teacher helps students in planning and preparing appropriate work such as reports, videos, and models as well as helping them to share assignments with their friends, 5) Stage 5 (Analyzing and evaluating the problem solving process): At this stage, the teacher helps students to reflect or evaluate their investigations and the quality of the processes carried out.

Based on the situation analysis that has been carried out, the problems faced by partners can be identified as follows: 1) Socialization of training on problem based learning models is still rarely carried out, 2) Teachers do not yet know the design of problem based learning models, 3) Teachers do not understand management well. problem based learning model. This community service activity aims to: 1) Provide outreach to teachers about problem based learning models, 2) Provide understanding to teachers about designing problem based learning models, 3) Provide understanding to teachers about learning model management problem based learning.

Influence will attract qualified, intelligent, and trustworthy people. Including, people who have self-leadership in the strength of integrity, motivation, competence and reliable capacity. A leader is a person who holds authority and power within the power of influence. The higher a person's level of leadership, the wider his influence in exercising the authority and power he has. And the lower a person's level of leadership, the less influence he has in terms of authority and power.

If carried out, it can be identified that the problems faced by partners are as follows: 1) Socialization of training on problem based learning models is still rarely carried out, 2) Teachers do not yet know the design of problem based learning models, 3) Teachers do not understand well the implementation of problem based learning models. This community service activity aims to: 1) Provide outreach to teachers about problem based learning models, 2) Provide understanding to teachers about designing problem based learning models, 3) Provide understanding to teachers about implementing learning models problem based learning.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach, one of the most appropriate ways to reveal and interpret various symptoms and phenomena of educational strengthening management to improve student academic achievement in the city of Sukabumi. where data collection is carried out using descriptive analysis methods, which always maintains the integrity of the subject, the data collected is analyzed more comprehensively.

The collected data was then analyzed using the content analysis method namely to find management concepts for strengthening education on student academic achievement so that the sources studied have a relevant focal point in research. Using the content analysis method, the collected data can be described as including: (1) Credibility, Dependability, Confirmability, Transferability (2) data presentation, which was used in this research using in-depth interviews, participant observation and documentation studies, (3) drawing conclusions/ verification, namely drawing conclusions in response to the research focus.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Management Problem Based Learning Model

Implementation of Based Learning model management activities as planned, namely in the form of training which includes: a) Providing material on the importance of the problem based learning model and combining it with existing resources, b) Providing material about learning concepts using the problem based learning model, c) Providing training for teachers to design learning using the problem based learning learning model, d) Providing training to teachers in implementing learning using the problem based learning learning model, e) Guidance and consultation clinics for learning model management via the WhatsApp group, e) Practice management of the problem based learning model in accordance with subjects taught in each school, f) Monitoring, Evaluation and Follow-up.

The success of the objectives of this community service activity can be determined by conducting an initial assessment and at the end of the activity. To find out the initial assessment is carried out with an initial exam (Pre Test), and to find out the final assessment is carried out with a final exam (Post Test). This activity is part of a series of activities. The results of the process assessment obtained the following information; 1) Participants were very enthusiastic about the course of the activity, this was indicated by several participants asking questions and being proactive during the training. This is supported by the excellent presentation of material by the resource persons. Likewise, several questions submitted by the resource person were answered well. This is an indicator that this community service activity can be said to be successful; 2) Understanding material regarding concepts, principles, design and implementation of the PBL model is very important for teachers to know as a basis for teachers to develop further in the classes they are responsible for. Apart from that, so that teachers can measure and follow a precise and efficient learning process. Delivery of training and guidance material through simulations and guided exercises regarding problem based learning model management really helps participants understand the material presented by the resource persons; 3) Guidance, training and presentations on the steps for implementing problem based learning models that are adapted to the teaching material are the core material of these activities, which in the end the teacher understands and can implement the problem based learning model. The monitoring and evaluation stage is the stage to find out dedication that has been done. This stage includes measurements with the following instruments: 1) Test; The instrument test is used to see teacher knowledge about the importance of learning models and the steps of problem based learning models, as well as evaluating model management. 2) Portfolio; An instrument in the form of a portfolio is used to determine the teacher's ability to 1) create learning tools using the problem based learning model and 2) carry out learning using the problem based learning model. Meanwhile, test results and portfolios are used as material for consideration and input for future improvements. The follow-up to this activity is facilitating the teachers in the form of a clinic online learning through WhatsApp groups so that friendships are not broken and there is a forum for communicating various obstacles and also sharing best practices from implementing the problem based learning model between schools. Based on the description of the results of the activity, several things are explained as follows: Problem Based Learning is a learning model that can train students to learn and work together in groups in an effort to find solutions to solve real problems. The problem based learning model has the idea that learning can be achieved if educational activities are focused on tasks or problems that are authentic, relevant, and presented in a context. Through this method, the aim is for students to have real experience that will be useful in facing their lives in the future. This experience is very important because effective learning starts from concrete experience. Questions, experiences, formulations, and conceptualization of problems that they themselves create are the basis for learning.

The initial conditions of the pretest and posttest can be seen that there is an increase in knowledge from before the service activities were carried out to after being given knowledge about problem based learning model management. As a follow-up to this activity, participants are expected to be able to apply the results of the training in carrying out their duties. So that

the results obtained can really see the results and progress of learning for themselves. If this is done well, using correct and sustainable procedures, it can create professional teachers who are adaptive in an increasingly competitive era. Teachers should be able to carry out similar activities and always actively participate in various activities in the Subject Teachers' Deliberation forum (MGMP) and in the Association forum to open their horizons and confirm various problems in learning in their classes through sharing good practices with other teachers. This activity is an effort to have a positive impact and influence on teachers to always try to improve their ability to carry out learning, including the ability to manage problem based learning models. The results of this service are in line with research conducted by Pujiati (2017) which concluded that the problem based learning model management was able to increase student competence. Apart from that, the results of this service are in line with Arnyana's opinion which states that "Educators' efforts to build 4C skills in the 21st century can be implemented through various forms of learning models that are more directed at solving authentic problems that can be solved cooperatively, so that they can increase students' learning activeness ". (Arnyana, 2019: 5). The results of this service also strengthen the aim of the problem based learning model, namely to solve problems that are authentic (real) and function to produce changes in behavior and mastery not only conceptually, but also to produce a solution through new experiences (Ibrohim in Sontani, 2016:42).

CONCLUSION

The management of the problem based learning model in improving the quality of learning can be concluded that the problem based learning model can be used effectively in increasing students' learning activeness, so that the quality of learning can be achieved well. Management of problem based learning models for teachers needs to be supported through various forms of education and training. This statement is consistent.

Based on the opinions of these experts, researchers concluded that a learning model is a learning pattern that is depicted from the beginning to the end of the process learning that is presented typically by the teacher to achieve learning goals. One learning model is a PBL (Problem-based learning) based learning model. The PBL (problem based learning) based learning model is innovative learning that is student centered and establishes teachers as motivators and facilitators, where students are given the opportunity to work autonomously to construct their learning. 5 The problem based learning (PBL) model is a learning model that involves a problem in the learning process.

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